

U.S. NUCLEAR ENERGY
AFTER THREE MILE ISLAND AND CHERNOBYL

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ABSTRACT

Commenting on the failure of the United States to implement a sound energy policy to mitigate the effects of the energy crisis of the 1970s, then Secretary of Defense Harold Brown declared, "There is no clearer or more serious threat to the longterm [sic] security of the United States and to its Allies than that which stems from the growing deficiency of secure and assured energy resources."(1) Focusing on one aspect of this national problem, Barry J. Smernoff, a consultant on national security affairs, states that "the postwar research emphasis on nuclear fission and the outright failure to anticipate, study, and resolve the interlocking sociopolitical problems engendered by the widespread utilization of nuclear energy constitute a massive failure of American science and engineering".(2) He attributes this serious breach in U.S. energy security to ". . . the acute lack of foresight demonstrated by the U.S. Government and the nuclear industry to examine the multiple problems that large-scale use of fission energy would entail."(2) Although the critic's hindsight is often perfect, this is still a stinging indictment of a technology that was forecast to produce electricity "too cheap to meter." President Eisenhower's Atoms for Peace program initiated nuclear power in the United States. Nixon's Project Independence, an effort which promised to supply half of this Nation's electricity from nuclear plants by the year 2000, was billed as guaranteeing energy self-reliance leading to greater U.S. security in the often forecast world energy crisis.

Electricity is generated from two primary energy sources, burning fossil fuels and nuclear fission. Of the fossil fuels, coal is plentiful in the United States, but its increased use is not environmentally acceptable. Oil and natural gas are becoming scarce. Renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power have not been developed on a large-scale. Fusion, the energy of the sun, will not be available until well into the next century. The only real alternative to satisfy the increasing demand for electricity is nuclear power. Without secure, reliable, and safe energy sources to fuel the expanding, high tech economy, the national security will be jeopardized.

Unfortunately, a U.S. Congress Office of Technology Assessment report released in 1984 stated that nuclear power plants currently present utilities with too many financial risks to justify continued use. These risks include a fluctuating demand for electricity, enormously high construction costs, burdensome government regulations, unforeseen operating problems, and, most surprisingly, growing public opposition. The study further suggested that "if the nuclear [power] option is foreclosed, it should at least happen with foresight, not accident or neglect" and reaches the conclusion that ". . . there is no simple key to restoring nuclear power as a national energy option."(3) The purpose of this paper is to explore the current state of nuclear power in the U.S. with particular emphasis on the effects of the nuclear accidents at the Three Mile Island (TMI) nuclear plant in 1979 and most recently at Chernobyl.

THE U.S. NUCLEAR POWER INDUSTRY IN PERSPECTIVE

As of 31 December 1985, 93 nuclear power plants were in operation in the United States supplying nearly 400,000 Megawatts (MW) of electrical power, or about 16 percent of that consumed. An additional 26 facilities were under construction. The U.S. is by far the largest user of nuclear power, exceeding France by nearly 200 percent and the Soviet Union and Japan by almost 250 percent. The surge in nuclear power growth occurred in the 1960s and 1970s. However, even with such impressive statistics, the U.S. nuclear power industry is now at a virtual standstill. No new nuclear plants have been ordered since 1978 and since 1974 over 100 reactors have been canceled. It may be well after the year 2000 before a utility orders another nuclear reactor. The problems now facing the nuclear power industry can be traced back to the end of the Second World War, the beginning of the atomic age.

Following the atomic attacks on Japan, many Americans felt the Nation's guilt could be erased by harnessing the tremendous power of the atom for peaceful purposes. Unfortunately, many of the optimistic predictions about the future of nuclear power were based upon insufficient knowledge of the problems and dangers involved. Many reactor safety issues and malfunctions encountered later were

unknown at that time. Even the health effects of radiation were not recognized. Nevertheless, the Nation charged off into the nuclear unknown with the President and Congress in the lead.

Congress established the Atomic Energy Commission (AEC), later called the Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC). with passage of the Atomic Energy Act in 1946. Given virtual autonomous power, the AEC embarked on an ambitious program to convince the electric utilities to invest in nuclear power. The AEC was successful through a combination of veiled threats that the government would build nuclear plants unless the utilities did and the offer of enormous financial inducements. Economic encouragements included free nuclear fuel for five years, only token damage liability even for gross negligence, and research and development subsidies to build huge, full-scale power plants.

The nuclear power industry experienced phenomenal growth in the mid-1960s, with 29 applications for new reactors submitted in 1967 alone. By then, the amount of nuclear capacity on order exceeded that in operation by a factor of 28. The capacity of plants under construction increased from 300 MW in 1962 to 700 MW in 1965 and 1,150 MW in 1972. The economy of scale argument is valid only when small demonstration projects are successful. In the nuclear power case, they were not. Experience in operating the first, small-scale reactors soon uncovered serious technical difficulties. Many of the early projects encountered cost overruns and construction delays. Some experts in the industry began to realize that nuclear power was neither technically feasible nor economical, and quite probably unsafe. However, the AEC continued to emphasize only the progress made in developing this new technology and encouraged utilities to build even larger reactors.

By the time the safety problems came to light, many reactors had already been built or were under construction. Safety retrofits ordered by the AEC were very expensive, contributed to the complexity of the plants, and usually caused delays and extended shutdown periods. Because of the many plants being built, the available construction contractors were pressed to the limit. This led to mismanagement and shoddy workmanship, thereby increasing the cost of new plants. Since the plants were getting larger, each design was different, compounding the construction and license approval process. Average time to build a plant went from six years to 12 and costs increased by as much as 10 times.

As if these problems were not enough for the nuclear power industry, the Arab oil embargo of 1973 and the worldwide recession of 1974-75 changed many Americans' thirst for energy. Growth in demand for electrical power, which had been very stable and predictable, unexpectedly declined as Americans began to conserve. Even though nuclear power was heralded as the only energy option which would eliminate the dependence on foreign oil, actual operating costs rose dramatically. When the operating cost differentials between nuclear and coal-fired plants evaporated, new orders came to a

halt. More significantly, many new plants on order were canceled.

While the financial ramifications from the events of 1973-75 were truly significant, safety problems shook the very foundations of the nuclear industry. Many of the complex systems were not thoroughly understood by the operators. As more plants came on-line, human and mechanical errors became more numerous. In 1975 a worker using a candle to search for air leaks started a fire at the Browns Ferry plant in Alabama. Five emergency core cooling systems were damaged, nearly triggering a meltdown of the reactor core. Incidents like this, as well as those at other plants were omens the forthcoming turmoil that lay in the very near future.

THE NUCLEAR POWER INDUSTRY IN TURMOIL

A 1957 Atomic Energy Commission study estimated that a major accident, such as a core meltdown at a large nuclear plant, would release intensely radioactive gases, particles, and water, could kill 3,400 people, injure 43,000 more, and cause up to \$7 billion in property damage (1957 dollars). Lethal distances could extend up to 15 miles from the plant and the health danger zone could have a radius of 45 miles. An area of over 150,000 square miles could be contaminated, or almost 5 percent of the landmass of the continental United States (the size of Illinois, Indiana, Ohio, and half of Pennsylvania).

The beginning of the end of what some nuclear power proponents call the first nuclear era began in the early morning hours of 28 March 1979. The 880 MW Unit 2 reactor of the nuclear plant at Three Mile Island, near Harrisburg, PA, was severely damaged by a loss of reactor coolant. Several emergency systems failed. The situation was further exacerbated by erroneous operator actions as they struggled to regain control of the reactor.

More than half of the reactor core was damaged. Even though the accident occurred over seven years ago, barely a third of the recovery work has been done. The cleanup effort is estimated to cost \$1.4 billion and may take many more years to complete. Unit 2 will probably never be restarted. The plant cost \$700 million to build and only operated three months before the accident. Unit 1, situated next to the stricken reactor, was restarted in October 1985, also after six unproductive years. As a result of the accident, the utility owning and operating the Three Mile Island nuclear power plant came very close to bankruptcy.

Although partial core meltdowns had occurred in at least three separate prior instances to TMI, (at AEC facilities in 1959 and 1966 and at the Enrico Fermi breeder reactor near Detroit in 1966), the TMI accident spelled doom for the U.S. nuclear power industry. The movie "The China Syndrome," graphically and dramatically highlighting nuclear power safety problems had first been shown only two weeks before the TMI accident. It served to sensitize the public to the perceived catastrophic dan-

gers of a major accident. Only a small amount of radioactive gas was released from the TMI plant, but an estimated 140,000 people evacuated the area anyway. Utility and NRC spokesmen contributed to the loss of credibility by appearing either not to know or understand just what had happened. "What shook the public the most was seeing the men in white lab coats standing around and scratching their heads because they didn't know what to do. The result was that accidents were taken seriously in a way they never had before," stated NRC Commissioner Victor Gilinsky, a critic of the industry (4).

The lessons learned from TMI cost the industry billions of dollars and, coupled with the downturn in demand for electricity, has been the prime contributor to the hiatus in nuclear power development. Over 6,000 additional safety steps were ordered by the NRC. Reforms spanned the spectrum from operator training to new evacuation plans to a myriad of additional, complex safety devices. The NRC also added many new, tough regulations and safety standards. Half of the NRC-mandated safety procedures were instituted after TMI. Compliance has led to extended construction times, incredible cost overruns, and project abandonments. The licensing process has been lengthened from seven to eight years to the current 10 to 15 years. Long Island Lighting's Shoreham plant cost estimate was originally \$241 million in 1965. The plant has taken 18 years to build with the price skyrocketing to \$4 billion dollars. Initial start-up is still delayed by local government opposition to the required evacuation plan.

Perhaps the most significant impact on the U.S. nuclear power industry was the dramatic decrease in electrical energy demand since the accident at TMI. Demand for electricity increased by only 1.7 and 0.3 percent in 1980 and 1981 respectively. Increases had previously been averaging almost 7 percent annually. In 1982, demand shrank by 2.3 percent, the first decline since World War II. Because of dwindling demand, there is now about 30 percent more generating capacity than needed. This includes coal plants as well as nuclear. Not unexpectedly, utilities are abandoning nuclear projects that were nearly complete as the operation and construction costs are soaring beyond those of the coal-fired plants. Nuclear plants can now be built for \$3,000 per kilowatt (kW) while coal-fired units cost only \$1,200 per kW. Well known projects recently canceled include Marble Hill in Indiana (\$2.5 billion spent), Zimmer in Ohio (97 percent complete and over \$1.7 billion invested), and Michigan's Midland project (85 percent complete, \$3.4 billion spent) (4). In fact, since TMI there have been no new reactors ordered in the U.S. and 36 new units have been canceled. Don Beeth of Houston Lighting and Power was quoted as saying, "The first lesson we've learned is 'Don't build nuclear plants in America.' You subject yourself to financial risk and public abuse." (4) Charles Komanoff, a New York energy analyst, sums up the situation quite well. "The fundamental problem facing nuclear power is that it's just too expensive. At some point the costs just got out of control." (5)

"A serious accident cannot happen." This phrase had been repeated so often by the nuclear power industry that everyone became convinced that it was true. Speaking to the NRC, William Stratton of the American Nuclear Society urged a reevaluation of the NRC licensing regulations and procedures when he remarked, "It's very clear that for the long-range future, it is not in the public interest to design, operate, and regulate nuclear power plants on the basis of hypothetical accidents that are physically impossible." (6) The recent nuclear catastrophe at Chernobyl in the Soviet Union graphically demonstrated not only the fallacy in that argument, but the high price that must be paid for a lapse in technical vigilance.

Ironically, the most serious accident in the history of nuclear power resulted from a safety test gone awry. Located 80 miles north of Kiev in the Soviet Ukraine, the destroyed Chernobyl Unit 4 is part of a huge nuclear power complex. Four 1,000 MW units were in operation, with two more, Chernobyl 5 and 6, under construction. Two massive steam and hydrogen explosions blew off the 1,000 ton steel cover plate. This exposed the reactor core to the open atmosphere and set fire to the power plant building and the graphite material which moderated the nuclear fission reaction. During the course of the disaster, more long-term radiation was released into the environment than all the nuclear tests and bombs ever exploded. Radiation readings as high as 2500 times the normal level were experienced as the reactor exploded on 26 April 1986, expelling over 8 tons of highly radioactive material. The resulting damage statistics are staggering; 31 dead, \$2.7 billion in direct costs, 135,000 people evacuated to temporary housing, 310,000 children (most susceptible to radiation) sent away to summer camp early, and 1,000 square miles of farmland contaminated. "The accident took place as a result of a whole series of gross violations of operating regulations by the workers," admitted Andronik M. Petrosyants, chairman of the Soviet Committee for the Peaceful Uses of Atomic Energy (7).

International reaction to the Chernobyl nuclear disaster has been mixed. Most nations severely criticized the Soviets for not warning the world of the accident and the nearly two weeks of official silence concerning the situation. Anti-nuclear feelings in Europe were the highest due to the close proximity. Nuclear power plants proposed and under construction in Austria, the Netherlands, Norway, Denmark, and Yugoslavia are expected to be halted. There is considerable sentiment in Sweden to completely abandon nuclear power by the year 2010. Its twelve nuclear plants now supply 42 percent of the nation's electrical power. Interestingly, the Soviet Union views nuclear power as essential in light of that nation's dwindling coal and oil reserves and their nuclear program apparently will continue unabated.

Since the U.S. was little affected by the Chernobyl radioactive fallout, reaction has not been as strong. Spokesmen for the nuclear power industry pointed out that American reactors are of a completely different design and have been stres-

sing that such an accident could not happen in the United States. A group representing the nuclear power industry plans a massive public relations campaign to show the superiority of American technology, engineering, and operating practices. Antinuclear groups have called for more strict licensing and operating regulations. They hope to convince the Congress to significantly increase the liability of the nuclear power industry when the liability limiting Price-Anderson Act comes up for review next year. "Although they are putting up a brave front, nuclear industry insiders privately concede that the name of the game is really damage control."(8)

IS THERE A FUTURE FOR NUCLEAR POWER IN THE UNITED STATES?

"It's important not to lose sight of the considerable role nuclear energy plays. Very little attention has been paid to the pluses, too much to the negative side of the industry. I would not over time write off the nuclear option."(4) These were the 1984 words of Commonwealth Edison Chairman James O'Conner as he surveyed the future of nuclear power. Other experts agree. Edward Merrow of Rand Corporation feels that "it is the only real energy alternative that appears viable."(4) Although the safety implications of the nuclear accidents at TMI and Chernobyl have and will continue to be profound, the future of nuclear power in the United States rests on the economic issues as well. If the nuclear power industry cannot build nuclear plants that operate safely and economically, then the nuclear option will indeed be foreclosed.

Two major arguments for nuclear power are that other forms of energy are not sufficient to meet U.S. demands and that nuclear energy is less harmful on the environment than burning fossil fuels. A significant development has been the recent upward trend in electric power demand. Demand in 1984 was increased four percent over 1983. Some parts of the U.S., notably in the West, have experienced a seven percent growth rate due to the high tech requirements for electricity. New generating capacity will be needed to satisfy the additional need. Despite all of the negative criticism, nuclear power is becoming a major source of electrical energy, surpassing oil in 1980 and natural gas in 1984. This year it is expected that nuclear energy will be second only to coal as the Nation's leading source of electrical energy. With nuclear power supplying nearly 16 percent of the demand in the U.S., abandonment of this source would cost billions of dollars, severely strain efforts to achieve energy independence, and put a heavy burden on the environment because of the necessary increase in coal usage. Coal plants release thousands of tons of pollutants into the air every day and are the prime cause of the acid rain which is destroying many lakes, particularly in the Northeastern United States. Alternative or renewable forms of energy such as solar or wind power are not developed enough to produce energy in large quantities. Fusion, which promises the greatest hope for long-term energy independence, is still decades away. The nuclear option must be kept open to bridge the gap between fossil fuels

and the introduction of fusion power or the large-scale use of alternative sources.

Public opposition to nuclear power in the United States has grown since the accidents at TMI and Chernobyl. Prior to 1979, nearly 60 percent of those questioned favored the construction of more nuclear plants while about 25 percent were opposed. Following TMI, support fell to 50 percent, but opposition grew to 45 percent, reflecting a significant shift from the undecided group. In a poll taken shortly after the Soviet accident, 59 percent disapproved of building any more plants with only 34 percent in favor. A greater number, 73 percent, oppose construction of a nuclear plant within five miles of their home (9).

In order to restore public confidence and acceptance of nuclear power, reactors must be designed that can operate efficiently and safely. The probability of a serious accident must be zero. Safety should not depend on mechanical or human intervention, but on physical principles. Such inherently safe reactors would be small and operate at low temperatures so that heat could escape by natural conduction and radiation. No emergency cooling pumps would be needed. Control rods would also be unnecessary as the fission process would be controlled by maintaining a fine internal balance between the normal cooling water and the borated water which absorbs neutrons. If the pumps were stopped for any reason, the balance would be disturbed and the fission reaction would stop. A massive containment vessel could surround the reactor, designed to withstand everything but a direct hit by a nuclear weapon. The design would be standardized, streamlining the licensing requirements. Experts predict that such a plant would take ten years to develop.

In the meantime, Norman Rasmussen, professor of nuclear engineering at MIT, believes that "if the nuclear industry wants to survive, [it should] well and without problems, at high availability factors."(10)

CONCLUSIONS

The accidents at Three Mile Island and Chernobyl have underscored the fact that the American nuclear power industry is in serious trouble. The blame for all the many problems does not rest solely with the blunders that took place in 1979 and 1986. The seeds were sown when the nuclear industry began building large capacity plants too quickly, before it had developed enough experience and expertise. The unexpected downturn in electrical energy demand after the Arab oil embargoes left the utilities with excess generating capacity. The combination of these factors has led to an economic disenchantment with nuclear energy in the United States. As a result, no new nuclear power plants have been ordered since 1978 and many nuclear facilities have been canceled and abandoned. However, with the recent upturn in electrical demand, the Nation will soon have an energy shortfall. Solar, wind, or fusion power will not be available in the near-term to meet the increasing energy needs.

Secretary Brown believes "the United States should develop alternative supplies of energy, both conventional and non-conventional, to reduce demand on a depleting world resource base."(1) Furthermore, the Nation requires secure and abundant energy supplies that are independent of external influences. The energy must be available in the very near-term in order to bridge the gap until renewable energy sources can be suitably developed. Nuclear power is the only realistic option.

Public confidence in nuclear power can be restored by operating the existing plants safely and economically. Accidents in nuclear power plants will continue to occur until reactors that are more reliable, more economical, and inherently safe can be designed and constructed, leading to what Alvin Weinberg of the Institute for Energy Analysis at Oak Ridge calls "the second nuclear era." Only then can the promise of nuclear power be fulfilled, thereby guaranteeing the secured and assured energy supplies so vital to national security.

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